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PORTRAYAL OF WOMEN IN PERSIAN FICTION

Dr. Md. Jawaid Akhtar

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Persian

Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti Urdu Arabi Farsi University, Lucknow

ABSTRACT

One of the major characteristics of modern Persian literature has been inclusion of subjects and themes that are related to common masses. Writers and poets started to give space to issues that had to do with the general condition of people in the society. Though it was not a typically Iranian phenomenon, the idea was borrowed from the writers of the Western World and was possible because of exchange of literature, translation and a vital role was played by the rise of printing press. The condition of Iranian women was one of the popular themes that was picked up by the writers especially those engaged in fiction writing. Saeed Nafisi, Sadegh Hedayat, Hejazi , Jalal Aal Ahamd and his wife Simin Daneshvar and many others included issues of women in their fictions. This Research Paper delves into some of the popular writings of Persian fiction and tries to analyze the portrayal of women in their writings.

Introduction

Elements of fiction have been quite abundant Persian Literature. Right from the very beginning stories, tales and romances have been an integral part of the classical masterpieces produced in Persian speaking mainland. Hence classical prose may be accounted for the development of Persian fiction but the immediate source of fiction writing in true sense of the terms is translation from European books which greatly influenced the fiction writers not only in form but in matter also. In a loose sense, almost all modern fiction is social science. The characteristic feature of modern fiction, in contrast to the medieval romances and fairy tales, is its realistic depiction of contemporary society. If not true to all sorts of fictions, it can be applied fully to the category of fictions that have been classified as ‘Social Fictions’.

From the late Qajar period onwards, as Iran began to have increasing contact with the West, many sections of Iranian society, especially intellectuals, minorities, clerics and women, became increasingly aware of their nation's problems. Modern Persian writers started picking up issues and problems of contemporary society and making these issues reflected in their writings. Social changes and new values demanded a particular kind of literature which led the writers and authors to elaborate or if not so then

to hint in symbolic ways on the issues such as emancipation of women, their place in the society, their marriage and education, religious fanaticism, superstitious beliefs of the ignorant Iranians and modernization of Iranian society under the influence of Western culture and so on. There were many other issues related to the social problems and challenges, however, issues related to women were also prominent and became prevalent in later days.

The movement that culminated in the Constitutional Revolution was not confined to the revolutionary demands for more political openness and social rights for women and minorities, but was accompanied and complemented from the start by a cultural revolution that introduced many new forms to Iran, foremost among them, drama, novel, music, and later film. It was obvious that this revolutionary new reality called for a fundamental change in the perception and articulation of reality itself.

Efforts were made to transform the old modes of literary and artistic expression through heated and exciting debates. Some of the foremost advocates of this Cultural Revolution started a movement for creating what one of its proponents, Mohammad Ali Jamalzadeh, called a "democratization" of the Persian language. In his preface to *Yeki Bood Yeki Na Bood* (Once upon a Time), Jamalzadah writes

"Today Iran is behind on the road of literature compared to most of the countries of the world. In other countries literature has, in the course of time, gained variety; and thanks to this variety it has captured the soul of people from all walks of life, and has induced everybody, men and women, the rich and the poor from schoolboys to old men, to read; and it has thus caused spiritual development of citizens. But unfortunately in our Iran moving away from the norms set by the ancients has been regarded as a ruination of literature. Commonly the very substance of the Iranian political despotism, which is well-known the world over, dominates the matter of literature as well; that is to say when a writer holds his pen in his hand, his attention is directed solely to the group of the learned and the scholars, and takes no interest whatsoever in the others. He even ignores the many who are fairly literate and can read and comprehend plain, uncomplicated writings quite well. In short, the writer does not subscribe to "literary democracy." There is no doubt that such an attitude is deplorable, particularly in a country like Iran, where the ignorance and benightedness of the populace is the obstacle to any kind of progress." [*This translation of the preface is by Haideh Daragahi, "The Shaping of the Modern Short Story: Jamalzadeh's 'Preface' to Yeki Bud, Yeki Nabud," in Thomas M. Ricks, ed. Critical Perspectives on Modern Persian Literature, Washington DC: Three Continents Press, 1984, 110-11.*]

The idea of induction of common people, men and women and the downtrodden and marginalized in literary pieces got attraction from many writers and a number of Iranian authors and poets followed suit. Persian fiction writing gave space to such ideas and issues and gained popularity. Issues related to women were one amongst many of these issues and almost all the towering personalities of fiction writing such as Jamalzaeh, Sadiq Hedayat, Mas'ud Dehati, Saeed Nafisi, Mohammad Hejazi etc. did remarkable job in depicting social issues including status of women in their writings. Sadegh Hedayat's writings gave new dimension to the issues of women in Iranian society.

His writings depict many shades of women, each having some correlation with the status of women in Iranian society. These writings also reflected upon the treatment of women in general and how men of the society treated their women. Though they might not be a common phenomenon, they were not far from reality.

His stories, *Zende be-gur*, *Ayena-ye shekasta* (The Broken Mirror), and *Arusak-e posht-e pardeh* (The Mannequin behind the Curtain), feature a young, educated Iranian male protagonist unable or unwilling to reciprocate a normal romantic relationship with a girl who is attracted to or loves him. The three protagonists are shy loners, who reject the girls in question, two of whom meet tragic ends. In *Ayena-ye shekasta* the blond and beautiful Odette, whom Jamshid has left, apparently commits suicide. In *Arusak-e*

posht-e pardeh Mehrdaad, having fallen in love with a mannequin that he takes back with him to Tehran, rejects Derakshande, his fiancée from childhood. Derakshande tries to win Mehrdaad back by dressing herself like the mannequin and startles Mehrdaad by standing in the mannequin's place and then responding to Mehrdaad's touch. However she gets killed by Mehrdaad and this act of killing by the protagonist has been seen by many as symbolic of a man's psyche or of a patriarchal mindset. It is symbolic of the fact that women are appreciated only till they are silent or they do not respond, once they speak or start raising their voice they are silenced. In Aabji Khanom (The Spinster) an ugly, unloved older sister is driven to suicide by the marriage of her beautiful and loved younger sister. Such symbolic writing was common and gained huge appreciation not only in Iran but also in other parts of the world.

Novel Daastan e Ishq e Shehranaaz by Yhya Doulatabadi portrays status of women in general even though he apparently discusses the problems of a particular character. Yahya's association with Bahai's sect was mainly responsible for his views regarding the improvement of women's position in society.

Ali Mohammad Afghani's novel Showher e Aahu Khaam produced sensation among people because of its thought provoking nature and forceful style. The main plot of this novel reflects the miserable conditions of Iranian women through the characters of Aahu Kahanam and Huma. It condemns the subordination of wife to husband and also denounces the laws and customs which were unjustly imposed upon women.

Abbas Khalili's novels Ruzgaar e Siyah, Asraar e Shab, Intiqaaam and Isaan, all deal with one or the other aspect of contemporary life like women's right and their emancipation, forced marriage, evils of prostitution, and moral degradation of youth and so on. Rabia Ansari's book Janaayat e Bashar describes the story of two young girls of respectable families who are enticed away by a group of traffickers and sold to a brothel. This book is a biting satire on the so called civilized people of the modern age. Jahangir's Khalili's main plot of Man Ham Girye Kardeh Am revolves around the social problem of prostitution. This novel draws our attention to the plight of women and advocates for their emancipation. Jalal Aal e Ahmad, another fiction writer seems to be influenced by the three masters of Persian prose Jamalzadeh, Sadeq Hedayat and Bozurg Alvi. Apart from other writings his collection of short stories Zan e Ziyadi deals with issues related to women. His novel Dukhtare Rai'yat is about a miserable maid servant who is ill treated by the family she works with. She commits suicide as she is abducted by the son of the house and is unable to bear the shame.

Sadeq Chubak is another writer who has also dealt with this issue through his writings. Sadeq Chubak's first story of his collection *Kheyma-e shab-bazi* (The Puppet Show, 1945) unfolds when a young woman, Odra, is praying for a husband in a holy shrine. She finds only disappointment while trying to find a husband, however, when in the final scene of the story she tries, unsuccessfully, to lure a kerosene peddler to marry her, who already has three wives. Chubak's portrayal of Odrā, as an ordinary woman with sexual desires and needs whose religious performance at the shrine is transformed into an expression of her lustful desire for the holy man buried in the tomb, stood in sharp contrast with the typical image of women in Persian fiction. As observed by a critic, the sexual passion displayed in the portrayal of Odrā forces the reader to look at those human desires and drives that we tend to disregard and deny. [Ali Ferdowsi, "Jame'a shenasi-e khayr o sharr dar qeṣṣaha-ye Sadeq Cubak," *Tehran, 2001, pp. 175-6.*]

There was a commonly held belief in Southern Iran that if an illegitimate child is thrown into a sea it turns stormy. Keeping this as central theme Chubak wrote 'Chera darya tufani shoda bood' (Why Was the Sea Stormy), a love story of sorts between a truck driver and a prostitute. The thought processes of the characters and their conversation has been captured so beautifully this story has been described by many as his best short story. Issues of women find a place here also.

Similarly the works of Mohammad Hejazi such as Aaineh, Huma and Parichehra are amongst those needs a mention depicting women as leading characters.

Not only men but women themselves started to write fictions and portray the status of women in Iranian society. Simin Daneshvar's name stands tall in this area. Her novel *Shu va Shun* is a masterpiece and has received applaud from many corners of the world.

The novel, told from a female perspective, recounts the story of a middle-class family in Shiraz under foreign occupation in World War Two. It portrays the composition of the Iranian society in which Daneshvar grew up; occupying forces come into turbulent conflict with tribal politics and the innumerable social factions of which Iranian society is composed. The characters include a corrupt governor and officials, tribal chiefs, ambitious dowagers and a communist schoolmaster, plus British missionaries, spies, colonels and merchants. Daneshvar's sympathies lie with the traditional midwives, peasants, shepherds and domestic staff – ordinary people who, in her words, "have much to offer. They must be able to give freely and with peace of mind. We, too, in return, must give to them to the best of our abilities. We must, with all our heart, try to help them acquire what they truly deserve." [As quoted in *Simin Daneshvar's obituary published by Guita Rezakhlou in The Guardian on 22 march 2012*]

The central figures are a traditional but progressive couple, Zari and her landowner husband, Yusof, whose refusal to sell his grain to the British leads ultimately to his death. Zari is an "honourable and educated" woman who loves her husband and her children. But she would like to have been brought up to act more independently: "I wish the world was run by women. Women who have given birth and know the value of their creation. They know the value of endurance, patience and monotony and not being able to do anything for themselves ... if the world was run by women, there would be no wars." [As quoted in *Simin Daneshvar's obituary published by Guita Rezakhlou in The Guardian on 22 march 2012*]

A web of political intrigues and hostilities is created that leads to the novel's explosive and tragic end. The death of Yousuf and his burial has been portrayed so dramatically imaging the fate of an unyielding visionary hero being crushed by the forces of injustice and deceit reminds the metamorphic implications of novels title which indicate towards an ancient ritual of mourning in Iran. Simin's other fictions too have female characters at the centre and depict various faces of women in society.

Writers such as Zoya Pirzad, Fariba Vafi, Moniru Ravanpour, Farkhondeh Aqayi, Azar Nafisi, Shahrnoosh Parisipour, Goli Taraqi, Mahsa Moheb-Ali, Belqeys Soleymani, Mahboubeh Mirqadiri, Roohangiz Sharifianare included among the known figures in fictional literature who have won some important awards, and the works of some of them have been translated into foreign languages and welcomed by non-Persian readers. The presence of the confused female characters, involved in big or unimportant concerns of daily life and also the woman who searches for her identity and individuality, is among the most basic features of the works of writers whose names are mentioned above.

It is pertinent to note that the idea of modern prose writing in Iran was based on incorporating issues related to general masses and issues of women was definitely to be figured with prominence. The writers did give this theme considerable amount of space in their writings and we find abundant literature especially Persian fictions that have been woven in the backdrop of these issues.

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